

COMPONENTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL COMPETENCE OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada axloqiy tarbiya, yoshlarni tarbiyalash metodlari va shakllarini ishlab chiqish bo‘yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar, tarixiy manbalarda ta‘lim-tarbiya sohasining ta‘limiy-axloqiy yo‘nalishida yozilgan ko‘plab asarlar tahlili, ularning mazmun-mohiyatini yoshlarga singdirish, shu bilan birga yoshlarning Vatanga muhabbat tuyg‘ularini tarbiyalash, mehnatni qadrlashga o‘rgatish, tengdoshlariga bo‘lgan madaniy munosabatlarni rivojlantirish, shaxs sifatidagi nuqtayi nazarini qaror toptirish yo‘nalishlari belgilab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ta‘lim, tarbiya, axloq, odob, ta‘limiy-axloqiy yo‘nalish, metod, shakl, tadqiqotlar, oila, oliy ta‘lim muassasasi, madaniy munosabatlar, tarix zarchashmalari.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются направления нравственного воспитания, исследования по разработке методов и форм воспитания молодежи, анализ многих работ, написанных в исторических источниках в воспитательно-нравственном направлении воспитательно-образовательной сферы, их интеграция в молодежную сущность содержания, в то же время, направление воспитания у молодежи чувства любви к Родине.

Ключевые слова: образование, воспитание, мораль, порядочность, воспитательно-нравственное направление, метод, форма, исследование, семья, высшее учебное заведение, культурные связи, историческое наследие.

Annotation. This article discusses the directions of moral education, research on the development of methods and forms of youth education, the analysis of many works written in historical sources in the educational and moral direction of the educational sphere, their integration into the youth essence of the content, at the same time, the direction of educating young people’s a sense of love to Motherland.

Key words: education, upbringing, morality, decency, educational-moral direction, method, form, research, family, Higher Education institutions, cultural relations, historical heritage.

It is the same fact that in the process of globalization today, a serious struggle for human consciousness and thinking is going on in every old earth of the world. This struggle, once evil and once Cultural in appearance, gives a thoughtful look around each of us, motivates to sum up the processes of the world's peat with reason and contemplation. It is known that the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3 , 2019 “on additional measures to improve the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work”, on the implementation of the tasks set at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan on December 25, 2020 and the appeal to the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2020, as well as on January 19 ministries encourage cooperation with a number of State and public organizations.

The awakening breath in the essence of the words of the head of our state “when the body of the life of society is the economy, its soul, its spirit is spirituality” is in essence in harmony with the Call Of The Lord Navoi, and perseverance in creating the foundation of the third Renaissance-it once again meant how unequal power and spiritual So, with high spirituality, the body of the economy, which is the body of the life of society, includes Soul, Soul, which is endowed with vitality, unequal creator power. Spirituality and enlightenment in all times have been an unequal power, happiness, peace, creativity, criterion of harmony, spiritual purification and soul-raising blessing. Because he urged the nation, the people, so to speak, to live according to high qualities, moral criteria for maturation, to be always awake in the path of good without becoming a captive of selfishness, vanity, to make this world prosperous, to be burdened with beauty.

Now, as noted in the decision “on measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs”, our people, in particular, take to a new level the work on strengthening the social cooperation of state organizations, civil society institutions, media, and the private sector in this direction, establishing organizational and practical and scientific research work to protect young people from the shadow of ignorance,

The solution of existing problems is to further expand the scale and scale of the effectiveness and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in raising youth morale, the population of the country, first of all, in the hearts of young people. It requires strengthening the sense of belonging to the reforms carried out in our homeland, creating a unified system for coordinating work in the field, developing spiritual and moral competence of young people. In this regard, not only our republic, but also the methodology for the development of spiritual and

moral competence of young people in the world educational system, the mechanism of competitive training, the practical pedagogical system for the development of moral qualities of young people, interactive programs, the teaching models of which are harmonized with the ideas of technological progress, have been applied to the educational process. The United Nations World Declaration on Higher Education of the 21st century, Unesco program documents “reform and development of Higher Education” pay special attention to improving the quality of education in educational institutions worldwide, organizing modular education, further improving the methodology of spiritual and moral education of student-youth by introducing modern methods of teaching.

In the world Higher Education System, Research is being carried out to improve the methodology of professional socialization of young people, development of spiritual and moral competence, education of social activity and initiative. In developed countries such as the United States, Russia, Germany, France, China, Korea, modular training, blended learning (mixed learning), master classes, webinars are being organized in improving the methodology for growing student-youth thinking, early identification of abilities, improving the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education mechanisms. Various aspects of the spiritual and moral education process have been studied by many scientists in our republic and the possibilities of applying the results of these studies in the educational process have been recommended.

Some of these studies are aimed at analyzing a certain aspect of the process of spiritual and moral education, which is extensive, others are aimed at enriching the content of spiritual and moral education in the educational process and applying new methods in various educational courses, issues of improving the system of educational work in educational institutions are studied. **Scientific analysis.** Ways of using national values in the development of the spiritual and moral education process and fundamentals of National Education, pedagogical foundations of the formation of spiritual and moral culture, the formation of spiritual and moral education in the higher education system and the problem of spiritual and professional training of future specialists, especially on issues of effective organization of the system of educational Karimova N. Dj. Mahmudova, O.Musurmonova, Sh. Olimov, M.Quranov, N.X.Oripova, Z.Q.Ismailova, N.A.Muslimov, N.M.Ochilova, Y.P.Azarov, Z.E. The scientific work of the Azimovs analyzed the problem of the formation of spiritual and moral education in the higher education system and the spiritual and professional

training of future specialists. Consequently, professor O. Although the conclusions developed by Musurmonova are scientifically substantiated, attention should be paid to consistency in their recommendations regarding methods of implementation. Forms and methods for the formation of student-youth spiritual culture (conference lessons; seminar lesson; discussion lesson; practical lesson; game lesson; travel lessons; role-playing lessons; educational activities; excursion; round tables; work in small groups; methods for the formation of spiritual culture: problematic-controversial situation; comparative-explanatory analysis; work on artistic-educational works; creative work; conceptual analysis; logical analysis; embodiment analysis; interpretation of spiritual-moral values; independent work, etc.k.) the system plays an important role in the development of the methodology of spiritual and moral education. It is noteworthy that the classification of the directions of spiritual and moral education by stages of education is a leading feature of pedagogical studies at the time of independence. In particular, in a new study developed methodological recommendations on the theoretical improvement and implementation of the content, forms and methods of spiritual and moral education of students of professional colleges by Sh.Olimov, the author's comments on the organization of educational activities in the process of extracurricular activities are highlighted on the basis of the latest achievements of science.

Z.Ismailova's scientific work on the issue of moral education of student-youth personality in spiritual and educational work . Basic ideas such as prosperity of the motherland, peace of the land, welfare of the people, Perfect Man, social cooperation, interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance are defined as the criterion for the moral formation of the student's personality. It is recognized that the main characteristics of national and universal values are the holiness of the concepts of family, neighborhood, el-yurt, high respect for parents, neighborhood, society in general, love for the native language with the immortal spirit of the nation, tolerance, hard work, honesty, etc., are the main factors for the moral formation of student-youth personality. One of the important aspects of this dissertation can be said that in the process of spiritual and educational work, a model for the moral formation of the personality of students and young people is developed. The upbringing of the younger generation depends, first of all, on the professional skills of the educator. At this point, it can be noted that the future and prospects of the country largely depend on the teacher, his level, preparation, dedication, attitude to the work of teaching

and upbringing. A teacher can be a devotee of his profession only if he perfectly acquires the norms of professional ethics and etiquette. Today, the fact that such dedication is more important than ever further increases the relevance of the research work carried out in this area.

The formation of the qualities of pedagogical etiquette in young people is studied as a special object N.M.Ochilova's dissertation presented an analysis of the theoretical foundations and features of the problem, as well as effective approaches used in this regard. The study developed a model for the formation of the qualities of pedagogical etiquette.

In addition, the work studied the current state of moral education of students, the issues of manifestation of the necessary moral qualities for pedagogical activity, organized a special course entitled "Teacher's etiquette", in which the idea of organizing lectures on the topic "attitude of society to the teacher's personality", "attitude to society", "attitude to the motherland", "attitude to work", "attitude to

In this regard, Z.K.A special place is occupied by Ismailova's research work on the theoretical experimental methodological foundations of spiritual and moral education on the basis of the "idea of national independence: basic concepts and principles". It can be noted separately that it is advisable to develop the spiritual and moral competence of students by organizing the fundamental essence of the methodology of upbringing of a harmonious personality by the author; methods for the formation of behavior through the public; methods for the formation of social consciousness and morality; methods of self-management and upbringing; division into methods of. As a result of the formation of spiritual and moral knowledge as part of spiritual and moral education, several moral categories are formed in student-youth, such as happiness, conscience, duty, Justice, honor, love, goodness, glory, faith, loyalty. In students-young people who have mastered spiritual and moral knowledge, such qualities as Initiative, social activity, patriotism, honesty, hard work, humility, dedication begin to find decisions. Young people with these qualities consciously fulfill the requirements of moral standards, national and universal values are in respect for the considered spiritual heritage, traditions and traditions. But having knowledge of spiritual and moral standards, understanding it, composing noble qualities does not yet mean that young people are spiritually-morally brought up. When the qualities of humanity are reflected in life experiences and are vividly manifested in the activity of an individual entering into a relationship, this determines the degree of his upbringing.

Stages of development of spiritual and moral competence in young people. It is advisable that the development of spiritual and moral competence in young people is carried out in specific stages. In this, first of all, it is necessary to be able to correctly set the goals and objectives of spiritual and moral education, determine the content of the work, organize a systematic approach to achieving the goal .

The purpose of spiritual and moral education was defined as follows: as a result of educational and educational activities carried out in educational institutions on a consistent basis, it consists in the training of a professional competent specialist with spiritual and moral qualities.

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